

Exploring Cognitive Characteristics in Weak Signals Perception within Science and Technology foresight

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Abstract: This paper systematically explores weak signal characteristics within science and technology (S&T) in its early perception, aiming to uncover future trends and enhance technological risk prevention. It begins by summarizing weak signal connotations and lifecycle characteristics, followed by a bibliometric analysis of early weak signals in S&T forecasting. To dynamically grasp weak signal changes and transformations, the study analyzes signal dimensions between weak and strong signals, exploring characteristic differences and potential transformation paths from a cognitive and evolutionary standpoint. Early weak signals in S&T foresight are marked by obscurity and high uncertainty, posing perception challenges. By contrasting signal attributes, including low visibility, uncertainty, fragmentation, subjectivity, predictiveness, and implicit knowledge gaps, the study lays a theoretical foundation for early weak signal perception in S&T foresight research and practice.

Keywords: weak signals, early signals, information perception, emerging technologies, technology foresight

1. Introduction

Weak signals, serving as precursors to science and technology (S&T) advancement and emerging technologies, present the fundamental challenge of early information perception. Analyzing weak signals entails a complex cognitive process, shaped by decision-makers' past experiences, environments, and knowledge frameworks, often marked by subjective interpretations (Eulaerts et al., 2019). Furthermore, weak signals typically undergo prolonged incubation periods, rendering them challenging to identify, and possess traits like fragmentation and uncertainty. Depending solely on expert

intelligence may overlook weak signals beyond their cognitive scope, leading to incomplete comprehension and impacting the accuracy of S&T forecasts.

Currently, there is a scarcity of research on weak signal characteristics in S&T foresight and intelligence perception. This paper delves into the features and challenges of technology's weak signal intelligence perception from a cognitive standpoint. Initially, it synthesizes and examines weak signal connotations and characteristics throughout the technology lifecycle. Employing a systematic literature review, it scrutinizes research topics associated with weak signals for foresight, offering insights into ongoing research trajectories. Building on weak signal attributes and a cognitive framework, the paper systematically scrutinizes various signals lying between weak and strong categories, elucidating their distinctions and developmental pathways, thus attaining a systematic and evolutionary grasp of weak signals. Ultimately, by contrasting various signal, the paper identifies typical features of weak signals, laying a theoretical groundwork for early weak signal perception in S&T foresight.

2. Definition and Connotation of Weak Signals in a Lifecycle Context

Ansoff (1975), a pioneering figure in weak signal research, defines weak signals as "signs of change that may occur in the future." These signals serve as forward-looking indicators of future trends, changes, and emerging phenomena, emanating from both external and internal sources (Hiltunen, 2008; Dang, 2018). Estimating the proportion of weak signals within the total signal space is challenging due to their inherent complexity in perception. Nonetheless, researchers have attempted to establish thresholds for weak signals based on specific measurement objectives. El Akrouchi et al. (2021) propose, based on the Pareto principle, that weak signals typically comprise no more than 20% of the information generated (Thorleuchter & Van, 2013), although this value may vary depending on the data characteristics of the target domain. Moreover, according to the Weak Signal Index (WK), a very low WK value (below 1%) may indicate noise, with weak signal thresholds usually falling below 10%, while noise levels typically fluctuate between 0% and 5%. Thorleuchter (2013) sets the noise threshold at 0%-2% in his identification model, representing rarely occurring words devoid of meaningful information, while the weak signal threshold ranges from 2% to 6%.

This paper diverges from the earlier research perspectives by suggesting that the proportion of weak signals in information depends on how 'information perception' is defined. Traditionally, 'information' is construed as data or facts conveying knowledge or intelligence, with weak signals forming a small fraction. However, in the age of big data, the majority comprises yet unknown and potential weak signals (Lala, 2024) (Peng, 2024). From a perceptual standpoint, the stock of strong signals is minimal, potentially constituting less than 5%, representing just the tip of the signal iceberg. However, their

perceptual intensity is high. In contrast, weak signal stock is substantial, possibly accounting for 95% or more of all signal spaces. Yet, due to limited analysis techniques and tools, their perceived intensity remains low.

Figure 1 presents a schematic depicting weak signal within S&T foresight from a lifecycle perspective, highlighting characteristics of signal strength and quantity within this framework. Signal strength is at its lowest during the incubation phase, making it challenging to perceive, and becomes stronger as time progresses. Signals transition from weak to strong and can be categorized into three types: dark signals, weak signals, and strong signals. The 'early perception' in this study primarily refers to the emerging phase, preceding the 'breakout' stage and encompassing some budding stages.

In addition, Figure 1 forms the full spectrum data type for science and technology topic analysis. Three distinct strong and weak signals correspond to various development stages, foresight category and methods of S&T foresight, each carrying different levels of uncertainty. Dark signals during the data life cycle's gestation phase are elusive and highly uncertain, often leading to serendipitous discoveries. Detecting anomalies necessitates scenario analysis and horizon scanning methods. Weak signals emerging during development stages exhibit significant uncertainty, forming a crucial domain for analyzing emerging frontier technologies. Utilizing the conventional "white box" perception method for strong signal analysis often yields subpar recognition results, necessitating the aid of "black box" and "grey box" methods like deep learning and fuzzy statistics. Spanning from the data life cycle's explosive phase through the hot period to maturity and decline stages, it constitutes the "hot" topic identification domain in science and technology development. As information accumulates, data uncertainty diminishes, primarily addressed using high-frequency statistical analysis methods as it matures.

Fig 1: Schematic depicting weak signal within S&T foresight from a lifecycle perspective

Note: ● marks the weak signal threshold, curve thickness indicates signal strength.

3. Bibliometric Analysis of Weak Signal Foresight in S&T context

In this section, we employ a systematic review approach to understand the main research directions and progress in using weak signals for S&T foresight analysis, summarizing the characterization of weak signals in these studies and further exploring the features of weak signals.

3.1. Construction of Search Strategy

This study employs a systematic literature review approach to systematically understand the progress of using weak signals for S&T foresight research. Initially, a search was conducted in the Web of Science (WOS) core collection to obtain early weak signals for S&T forecasting. The search strategy primarily includes three elements, 'weak signals,' 'sensemaking,' and 'foresight' ('#weak signals and (#sensemaking or #foresight)'), aimed at obtaining relevant literature on the use of weak signals for S&T foresight analysis. To enhance semantic retrieval, we expanded the search elements, including similar and synonymous terms as search keywords and employed wildcard matching. 17,286 records were obtained. We further selected relevant literature in the fields of information science, library science, sociology, management, and business economics, and obtained 1,656 records. We then read and analyzed each item one by one, excluding papers in the fields of medicine, environment, climate, etc., and a total of 428 relevant records were screened

anticipation	bank	early indication	fdp
complexity	systemic risk	highlight	feature selection
ansoff	warning system	policymaker	new finding
future signal	probability	population	politic
futures study	financial market	twitter	public policy

There is a close relationship between weak signals, forecasting methods, and perceptual abilities. Forecasting techniques aid in interpreting the future possibilities and potential impacts of weak signals, while heightened perceptual abilities ensure timely capture, leading to a better understanding of their characteristics and significance. Additionally, the identification of weak signals in S&T foresight research remains in the theoretical exploration stage, necessitating further analysis of early weak signal characteristics.

3.3. Perception Characteristics of Weak Signals in S&T Foresight

Building upon existing research, this paper integrates various weak signal characteristics, outlining key perception features in S&T foresight theory and practice. Table 1 details these perception characteristics and representative studies on weak signals perception in S&T Foresight.

Table 3: Overview of Weak Signal Characteristics in S&T Foresight

Characteristics	Perception Characteristics of Weak Signals in S&T Foresight	Representative Studies
Fragmentation	Gathering weak signals of emerging technology from diverse platforms like technology news, academic papers, patent databases, and social media presents a substantial challenge. Integrating these fragments into a coherent framework is difficult due to their diverse origins, hindering a comprehensive understanding.	Schoemaker et al. (2013) Endsley (2015) Deng et al. (2016)
Low frequency & high-growth	In the rapidly changing technology landscape, information on weak signals can fluctuate swiftly. For new technologies, products, or emerging markets, it's crucial to quickly assess the rate of change and adjust technology strategies accordingly.	Yoon (2012) Ma et al. (2023)
Ambiguity & instability	Emerging technologies and innovative concepts often carry ambiguity, especially in their early stages. When addressing weak	Hiltunen (2008) Dang (2018)

	signals related to future technology trends, this ambiguity can appear as vague technology descriptions or incomplete definitions of new concepts.	
Foresight	Gaining deep insights into emerging technology trends requires strong predictive abilities. This calls for an intelligent perception system capable of early detection and nuanced interpretation of S&T weak signals. Such a system reveals innovation opportunities and future trends effectively.	Rosse (2009) Liu & Xu (2021) Xu et al. (2023)
Subjectivity	Interpreting weak signals in technology can be influenced by subjective viewpoints of domain experts. To ensure thorough analysis, integrating perspectives from various professional fields is essential.	Kuosa (2011) Dong et al. (2018)
Low visibility, complexity, non-linearity	Emerging technological concepts often have minimal coverage, with low visibility, nonlinearity, and complexity—key traits of weak signals. Hence, it's crucial for the intelligence perception system to swiftly capture these emerging, low-visibility signals.	Kuosa (2011) Yoon (2012) Kim et al. (2016)
Contains knowledge gaps and opportunities	Weak technological signals often emerge in emerging technological domains that haven't gained widespread attention. Recognizing and understanding these signals not only fill knowledge gaps in the research field but also provide vital insights for future innovation efforts.	Yoon (2012) Kaivo (2012) Garcia & da Silva (2019) Zhang et al. (2023)

4. Multidimensional classification of weak signals from a cognitive perspective

This paper places weak signals within the wider signal space to comprehend their characteristics thoroughly by contrasting them with signals ranging from weak to strong. Notably, weak signals display significant 'subjectivity' (Eulaerts et al., 2019), rendering their analysis a 'complex and challenging cognitive journey.' Therefore, we integrate cognitive dimensions with signal attributes. Through a cognitive lens, we analyze potential weak signals across various dimensions like uncertainty, potential impact, and cognitive domains. This holistic approach facilitates the identification of weak signals and deeper insight into emerging technological trends.

4.1. Multidimensional Quadrant Classification from an Evolutionary Perspective

From a perceptual standpoint, weak and strong signals aren't strictly binary, with subjective boundaries between them remaining unclear. Moreover, weak signals may evolve into strong signals over time. Analyzing weak signals requires referencing strong signals. Technology foresight demands a systematic and evolutionary comprehension of innovation, heavily influenced by specific environmental conditions and task analyses. It calls for a coherent analysis of all innovation-related signals. Hence, to dynamically grasp signal changes and transformations, this paper introduces a quadrant classification chart for weak signals from an evolutionary perspective, encompassing weak and strong signals, as well as various intermediate types and their evolutionary trajectories.

4.2. Cognitive quadrant division

Former U.S. Secretary of Defense, politician, and military strategist Donald Rumsfeld introduced four concepts related to cognition: "Unknown Unknown," "Known Unknown," "Unknown Known," and "Known Known." These terms depict uncertainties in intelligence and challenges in knowledge management for decision-making (Logan, 2009). "Unknown Unknown" refers to areas not understood nor recognized, "Known Unknown" denotes areas known but not comprehended, "Unknown Known" refers to areas understood but are not aware of, and "Known Known" signifies both known and understood areas. This classification mirrors various human cognitive states and aligns with signal strength perceptions, often applied in intelligence analysis and decision-making contexts.

This article categorizes signals into different areas based on two dimensions: uncertainty and potential impact, represented by "Unknown Unknown," "Known Unknown," "Unknown Known," and "Known Known." This multidimensional classification offers a nuanced understanding of weak signals, guiding technology decision-making, knowledge management, and innovation. Figure 3 presents a weak signal classification chart, combining the four cognitive types and their common methods. The horizontal axis denotes uncertainty, while the vertical axis represents impact, divided into low, medium, and high levels. This classification aids researchers and technology managers in efficiently addressing complex information perception and processing challenges, identifying innovation opportunities, mitigating risks, and improving uncertainty management abilities.

Fig 3: Weak Signal Perception Categories based on Uncertainty and Potential Impact

The S&T foresight research aims to minimize uncertainty in future development. Less available information increases intelligence value but also raises uncertainty. This trade-off underscores the importance of conveying uncertainty alongside foresight research and practice. Researchers must provide clarity on associated uncertainties to enhance S&T decision-making.

4.2.1. The "Unknown Unknown" Zone

The "Unknown Unknown" zone encompasses cognitive domains not currently recognized or predicted but with potential future influence. This area includes numerous "weak signals," "wild cards," and partial "dark data", typically marked by high uncertainty and significant potential impact (Kaivo-oja, 2012). These signals, often concealed and complex, pose challenges for categorization. However, they can profoundly shape the future, indicating upcoming trends or changes and harboring emerging cutting-edge technologies. Signals in this zone may thus become vital indicators of future trends, closely aligning with the characteristics of "weak signals" and "wild cards."

4.2.2. The "Unknown Known" zone

The "Unknown Known" zone comprises information or facts already known but often overlooked or not fully understood. Signals here typically exhibit higher-than-average uncertainty and lower potential impact. This area encompasses many "latent signals" (Donnelly et al., 2019) and "stagnant signals", (Kim & Lee, 2017) which may hold some potential impact but require further exploration. Comparatively, "stagnant signals" are rarer, less noticeable, and more uncertain but closely tied to technological trends. They may indicate future technology directions or opportunities with higher potential impact, bridging the gap between "Unknown Unknown" and "Unknown Known" cognitive realms. On the other hand, "latent signals" exhibit relatively high uncertainty, with slower growth rates and frequencies, necessitating prolonged observation for clarification. Their

association with technological innovation is uncertain, and their potential impact is weaker, aligning more with the "Unknown Known" domain.

4.2.3. *The "Known Unknown" zone*

The "Known Unknown" zone encompasses signals with relatively low uncertainty but high potential impact. While people are aware of certain information, it hasn't been fully understood. This zone includes "feeling signals" (Kim & Lee, 2017) and "well known but not strong signals," (Donnelly et al., 2019) which carry influential information or trends yet to gain widespread attention. Despite being easier to perceive than "stagnant signals," (Kim & Lee, 2017) "feeling signals" and "well known but not strong signals" retain a notable degree of uncertainty due to incomplete comprehension and utilization. Regarding potential impact, "well known but not strong signals" and "latent signals" may represent future trends despite their slower change rates, while "feeling signals" hold latent potential information but exhibit low correlation with existing technological trends. Their current impact is relatively small, necessitating further analysis for potential influence determination.

4.2.4. *The "Known Unknown" zone*

In the "Known Known" domain, numerous "strong signals" are well understood by researchers, with low uncertainty and impact. This zone typically includes mature technologies. Signal analysis here aims to deepen understanding of these signals and their effects. Common methods include impact analysis and silent revolution analysis, which blend historical data with current trends and future predictions to reveal the evolutionary paths and future potential of known signals, uncovering their inherent value further.

5. Conclusion

This article starts by examining the essence and traits of weak signals within S&T foresight. Employing a systematic review method, it utilizes bibliometric analysis to investigate weak signal identification in technological innovation. The study highlights that recognizing weak signals in S&T foresight is still primarily theoretical. Subsequently, taking a cognitive perspective, the article explores weak signals and related signals, situating them between weak and strong signals. It delves into the disparities in characteristics and potential evolutionary trajectories of weak signals, "wild cards", "latent signals", "stagnant signals", "feeling signals", "well known but not strong signals" and strong signals. This study thereby enhances comprehension of weak signal characteristics in technology foresight research and practice.

This article contrasts signal attributes across cognitive realms, highlighting key characteristics of weak signals: fragmentation, low frequency/high growth, ambiguity/instability, foresight, subjectivity, low visibility, complexity, non-linearity, and containing knowledge gaps and opportunities. These characteristics make weak signals difficult to distinguish from noise, rendering them often undetectable. They can blend into mainstream information, undermining conventional anomaly detection techniques.

Moreover, the association of numerous weak signals may involve causal conflicts and cross-domain challenges, further complicating analysis.

This study has limitations. While it outlines suitable data analysis methods for various data areas, the proposed cognitive characteristics in weak signal perception within S&T foresight but still lack practical application analysis. Future research should apply these characteristics to different fields, detecting and complementing perception categories and methods.

Author contributions

Haiyun Xu: Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

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Liu Chunjiang: Writing – review & editing, Supervision

Xin Zhang: Methodology, Writing – review & editing

Shuying Li: Writing – review & editing, Supervision

Competing interests

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